

A Bibliometric Analysis of the ‘Journal of Biofuels’: 2010 - 2023

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Abstract: ‘Journal of Biofuels’ is published by Diva Enterprises Private Limited, New Delhi. ‘Journal of Biofuels’ is a peer-reviewed journal of international reputation that publishes high quality original research papers and reviews. ‘Journal of Biofuels’ is playing an important role in the dissemination of theoretical and practical knowledge in the fields of ‘Biosciences’, ‘Biotechnology’, ‘Chemical Engineering’, ‘Biofuel Production’ describing biological mechanisms and processes that relate to the Biofuel Production and its effect on environment. Bibliometrics is a branch of science which deals with the application of mathematical and statistical techniques on Library and Information Science. This research article examines the contributions of the ‘Journal of Biofuels’ from different point of views. The tabular analysis finds out the volume-wise distribution of contributions, authorship pattern of contributions, gender-wise distribution of contributions, citation-wise distribution of contributions, types of publications cited, distribution of contributions on different micro-subjects and related subjects under the ‘Biofuels’ clearly and vividly. This paper gives a detailed description about the journal by the way of bibliometric analysis in a pinpointed manner.

Keywords: Bibliometrics, Biofuels, Biochemistry, Biotechnology

Introduction: Bibliometrics is a branch of science discipline which primarily throws light on the quantitative study of library and information science. In the year 1969, the British Librarian Allan Pritchard first coined the term “Bibliometrics”. Bibliometrics may be defined as the ‘quantitative analysis’ of the bibliographic characteristics of the research outcome of any subject discipline. Dr. S. R. Ranganathan, the father of Indian Library Science, coined the term “Librametry”. The meaning of the word “Librametry” is the application of mathematical and statistical techniques in Library and Information Science. Many years later, the specialists in the subject field of ‘Library and Information Science’ coined the term “Informetrics”. They opined that “Informetrics” is the application of mathematical and statistical techniques on ‘Information Science’. Bibliometrics is closely associated with ‘Scientometrics’. ‘Scientometrics’ is the analysis of scientific metrics and indicators. ‘Bibliometrics’ includes the micro-subjects like ‘Citation Analysis’, ‘Authorship Pattern’, ‘Bibliographic Coupling’, ‘Co-Citation Indexing’, ‘Micro-Subject wise Distribution of Articles’ and so many others. Therefore, it may be said that ‘Bibliometrics’ is the terminology which stands for the application of mathematical and statistical techniques to the study of bibliography and its other allied aspects.

Now, we are living in the “Knowledge Society”. Knowledge is a strategic resource which resides in human brain, corporate culture and also in different forms of knowledge medium like print and non-print. Libraries and Information Centres are the store houses of knowledge. Libraries and Information Centres are consisting of books and non-book materials. These are the primary resources of libraries and information centres. These resources have no value until it is utilized. These resources of libraries and information centres should be used by the potential users properly. For the proper utilization of information resources, the bibliometric studies are very much helpful for librarians and information professionals. Information Selection, Information Collection, Information Organization, Information Processing, Information Retrieval, Information Dissemination etc. are the principal house-keeping operations of Libraries and Information Centres. All These functions of libraries and information centers can be easy and quick through the application of proper bibliometric techniques. As we know that Information is the power, so we should have to keep in our mind that Information is the strategic resource for all. Information handling should be done very cautiously. All the Information related activities can be done smoothly through the application and use of different bibliometric tools and techniques. Acquisition and technical processing work of libraries and information centres can also be done successfully through the application of bibliometric techniques. Library and Information Science is gaining its importance and popularity for its interdisciplinary nature and application of sophisticated techniques.

‘Journal of Biofuels’ is published by Diva Enterprises Private Limited, New Delhi. ‘Journal of Biofuels’ is a peer-reviewed journal of international reputation that publishes high quality original research papers and reviews. ‘Journal of Biofuels’ is playing an important role in the dissemination of theoretical and practical knowledge in the fields of ‘Biosciences’, ‘Biotechnology’, ‘Chemical Engineering’, ‘Biofuel Production’ describing biological mechanisms and processes that relate to the Biofuel Production and its effect on environment. It is a Half-yearly journal published in June and December. The Journal has both print and on-line versions. The Print ISSN of this journal is 0976 – 3015; and the On-line ISSN of this journal is 0976 - 4763. This paper is a bibliometric study of the ‘Journal of Biofuels’ and this bibliometric study covers the Fourteen [14] volumes of the journal [i.e. from Vol. 1 (2010) to Vol. 14 (2023)]. The research paper examines the contributions from different point of views. The tabular analysis finds out the volume-wise distribution of contributions, authorship pattern of contributions, gender-wise distribution of contributions, citation-wise distribution of contributions, types of publications cited, distribution of contributions on different micro-subjects and related subjects under ‘Biofuels’ clearly and vividly. This paper gives an in-depth description about the journal by the way of bibliometric analysis in a pinpointed manner. The research article would be helpful for the research scholars, students and teachers in the field of Biofuels, Biochemistry, Biotechnology, Bioelectricity, Biogas, Biodiversity, etc. and especially this research article would be very helpful for the research scholars and teachers in the field of Bibliometrics / Scientometrics / Informetrics etc.

Objectives of the Study: -

The following are the objectives of this paper: -

1. To know the nature and extent of authorship.
2. To make an analysis of the research articles published in the Fourteen volumes of the journal [i.e. from Vol. 1 (2010) to Vol. 14 (2023)] in order to collect information on the facts and sub-facts within its purview.

3. To know the number of contributors according to the Gender (i.e. Gender-wise distribution of contributions).
4. To know the number of contributions published during the period under study.
5. To know the number of citations (i.e. books, journals, reports, thesis, newspapers, electronic documents etc.).
6. To identify the contributions under different micro-subjects and related subjects under the 'Biofuels'.
7. To identify the nature and extent of contributions published in the 'Journal of Biofuels'.
8. To make a thorough study of the 'Journal of Biofuels'.

Scope and Coverage of the Study: This paper is a bibliometric study of the 'Journal of Biofuels' and this bibliometric study covers the Fourteen volumes of the journal [i.e. from Vol. 1 (2010) to Vol. 14 (2023)] and there are twenty-eight issues covered by this study as each volume contains two issues. The paper examines the contributions from different point of views. The tabular analysis finds out the volume-wise distribution of contributions, authorship pattern of contributions, gender-wise distribution of contributions, citation-wise distribution of contributions, types of publications cited, distribution of contributions on different micro-subjects and related subjects under 'Biofuels' in a clear and vivid manner.

Spectrum of the 'Journal of Biofuels': - This journal publishes original research papers, review articles, reports, and communications screened by national and international researchers who are experts in their respective fields of study. The 'Journal of Biofuels' covers the following subject disciplines: - Biochemistry, Bioclimatology, Biodegradation, Biodiversity, Bio-dynamics, Bioelectricity, Bioethics, Biogas, Biogenesis, Biogeochemistry, Biogeography, Bio-electrochemistry, Biofuel production and utilization, Biosciences, Biotechnology etc. This journal is also covering the allied subject disciplines in addition to the abovementioned subjects.

Methodology of the Study: - Data regarding each contribution in relation to authorship, authors' institutional affiliation etc. were collected, scanned, examined and recorded on the slips in a systematic manner. Data pertaining to contributions on micro-subjects were also organized on the slips. Data about citations in the contributions were recorded on the separate slips. Data about the documents cited, name of the journal or the name of the book, title of the article or the title of the book, page number, volume number and issue number and other required data about the contributions were recorded accordingly. After collection of data in slips, all the slips were arranged systematically. Another matter of fact is that necessary data were also collected from documentary sources, institutional sources and human sources. Data collected in the above manner were duly analysed and tabulated. On the basis of analysis and tabulation, the findings and conclusions were drawn. Finally, the research article is the result of this research endeavour.

Data Analysis: -

Table 1: Volume-wise Distribution of Contributions

Year	Volume No.	No. of Contributions	Percentage (%)
2010	1	30	16.76
2011	2	15	8.38

Year	Volume No.	No. of Contributions	Percentage (%)
2012	3	12	6.70
2013	4	10	5.59
2014	5	12	6.70
2015	6	12	6.70
2016	7	14	7.82
2017	8	15	8.38
2018	9	14	7.82
2019	10	12	6.70
2020	11	9	5.03
2021	12	9	5.03
2022	13	8	4.47
2023	14	7	3.92
Total	=====	179	100.00

The above table shows that the maximum numbers of papers are published in this journal in the year 2010, and minimum numbers of papers are published in the year 2023. This study covers total 179 numbers of contributions which are published during the year 2010 – 2023.

Table 2 Authorship Pattern of Contributions

Number of Authors	Number of Contributions	Percentage (%)
One Author	18	10.05
Two Authors	39	21.79
More Than Two Authors	122	68.16
Total	179	100

After analysing the above table it can be said that maximum numbers of research articles are published in this journal are contributed by more than two authors. The authors are very much interested to publish their research articles in this journal by more than two. It is also clear from this table that the authors are least interested to publish their research papers singly in this journal. The authors are slightly interested to publish their research papers jointly by two in this journal.

Table 3: Volume-wise Distribution of Contributions According to Authorship Pattern

Volume No. and Year	One Author	Percentage (%)	Two Authors	Percentage (%)	More Than Two Authors	Percentage (%)
1 (2010)	1	5.55	5	12.82	21	17.22
2 (2011)	1	5.55	1	2.56	13	10.66
3 (2012)	3	16.67	1	2.56	10	8.20
4 (2013)	1	5.55	00	00	9	7.37
5 (2014)	1	5.55	2	5.13	10	8.20
6 (2015)	1	5.55	7	17.95	6	4.92
7 (2016)	1	5.55	3	7.70	11	9.01
8 (2017)	1	5.55	4	10.25	8	6.56
9 (2018)	00	00	3	7.70	11	9.01
10 (2019)	1	5.56	6	15.38	5	4.09
11 (2020)	2	11.12	3	7.70	4	3.28
12 (2021)	2	11.12	1	2.56	7	5.74
13 (2022)	2	11.12	1	2.56	4	3.28
14 (2023)	1	5.56	2	5.13	3	2.46
Total	18	100	39	100	122	100

From the above table it is clear that maximum numbers of research contributions by more than two authors published in this journal are in the year 2010 (i.e. 17.22%), and minimum number of research contributions by more than two authors are published in the year 2023 (i.e. 2.46%). It is also clear that maximum numbers of research articles published by two authors (jointly) in this journal are in the year 2015 (i.e. 17.95%) and minimum number of research contributions are published by two authors in this journal are in the year 2011, 2012, 2021 and 2022 (i.e. 2.56%). It can also be said from the above table that maximum numbers of research articles published by single author in this journal are in the year 2012 (i.e. 16.67%).

Table 4: Distribution of Contributors According to Gender

Gender	Number of Contributors	Percentage (%)
Male	402	70.40
Female	169	29.60
Total	571	100

The above table shows that there are totally 70.40% contributors of this journal are male and 29.60% contributors are female during the period under study [i.e. 2010 – 2023]. There are total 402 male contributors and 169 female contributors from volume 1 to volume 14 [Total Fourteen volumes under this study].

Table 5: Volume-wise Distribution of Contributors on the Basis of Gender.

Volume No	Year	Male Contributors	Percentage (%)	Female Contributors	Percentage (%)
1	2010	64	15.92	21	12.42
2	2011	56	13.93	19	11.24
3	2012	52	12.93	20	11.83
4	2013	48	11.94	17	10.05
5	2014	31	7.71	18	10.65
6	2015	29	7.21	16	9.46
7	2016	25	6.21	14	8.28
8	2017	24	5.97	08	4.74
9	2018	21	5.23	06	3.55
10	2019	11	2.74	07	4.15
11	2020	12	2.98	08	4.74
12	2021	10	2.49	06	3.55
13	2022	11	2.74	07	4.15

Volume No	Year	Male Contributors	Percentage (%)	Female Contributors	Percentage (%)
14	2023	08	2.00	02	1.19
Total		402	100	169	100

After analysing the above table, it can be said that maximum numbers of male contributors are in the year 2010 (volume 1) and minimum numbers of male contributors are in the year 2023 (volume 14). It can also be said from the above table that maximum numbers of female contributors are in the year 2010 (Volume 1) and minimum numbers of female contributors are in the year 2023 (volume 14).

Table 6: Distribution of Contributions According to Citations

Volume No.	Year	No. of Contributions	Number of Citations	Average
1	2010	30	408	13.60
2	2011	15	392	26.13
3	2012	12	356	29.66
4	2013	10	344	34.40
5	2014	12	163	13.58
6	2015	12	118	9.83
7	2016	14	101	7.21
8	2017	15	102	6.80
9	2018	14	98	7.00
10	2019	12	96	8.00
11	2020	9	74	8.22
12	2021	9	79	8.77
13	2022	8	71	8.87
14	2023	7	69	9.85
Total	=====	179	2471	13.80

From the above table it is clear that the average numbers of citations per contributions are maximum in the year 2013 [i.e. 34.40] and the average number of citations per contributions are minimum in the year 2017 in this journal [i.e. 6.8]. It is also clear from the above that Maximum numbers of citations are in the year 2010 [i.e. 408], and minimum numbers of citations are in the year 2023 in this journal

[i.e. 69]. It can be said from the above table that the average number of citations per contribution of this journal is 13.80 during the period under the study.

Table 7: Types of Publications Cited

Types of Publications Cited	No. of Citations	Percentage (%)
Books	496	20.08
Journals / Periodicals	661	26.75
Seminar / Conference Proceedings	276	11.17
Reports; Working Papers; Approach Papers	145	5.87
Thesis / Dissertations	207	8.37
Electronic Resources	572	23.15
Miscellaneous Documents [Government Documents, Daily Newspapers (Printed) etc.]	114	4.61
Total	2471	100

The above table shows that the Journals and Books are mostly cited by the authors. As we are now living in the age of electronic resources, the authors and researchers are also cited the electronic resources very frequently. The other documents like thesis, dissertations, working papers, reports, conference papers etc. are also cited by the authors in this journal.

Table 8: Distribution of Contributions According to Different Micro- Subjects and related subjects under the 'Biofuels'

Micro-Subjects	Number of Contributions	Percentage (%)
Biochemistry	17	9.50
Bioclimatology	15	8.38
Biodegradation	12	6.71
Biodiversity	13	7.26
Bio-dynamics	11	6.14
Bioelectricity	12	6.71
Bioethics	07	3.91
Biogas	09	5.02

Micro-Subjects	Number of Contributions	Percentage (%)
Biogenesis	05	2.80
Bio-Geochemistry	08	4.47
Bio-Geography	04	2.24
Bio-electrochemistry	07	3.91
Biofuel Production & Utilization	24	13.40
Bio-Sciences	13	7.26
Bio-Technology	22	12.29
Total	179	100

After analysing the above table it can be said that the maximum numbers of contributions published in this journal during this period under study is on 'Biofuel Production and Utilization', and 'Biotechnology'. It can also be said from this table that Biosciences, Bio-Chemistry, Bioclimatology, Biodiversity, Biodegradation, Bioelectricity and Bio-dynamics are also very much attracted subject fields of the authors regarding their fields of research. It is also clear from this table that Biogas, Bio-Geochemistry, Bioethics, Bio-electrochemistry, Biogenesis and Bio-Geography are the micro-subjects and related subjects come under the Biofuels. Many research articles are also published on the abovementioned micro-subjects.

Findings and Conclusion: - After completion of this study, it can be said that there are total 179 numbers of contributions under this study during the period covered [i.e. 2010 – 2023]. Out of these 179 research articles, there are 122 research articles are contributed by more than two authors, 39 research papers are contributed by two authors and only 18 contributions are contributed by single author. It is clear that maximum number of contributions are in the year 2010 [i.e. 30]. It can be said that maximum numbers of research contributions by more than two authors in this journal are in the year 2010, and maximum numbers of research articles by two authors (jointly) in this journal are in the year 2015. It is also clear that maximum numbers of research articles by single author in this journal are in the year 2012. There are total 402 male contributors and 169 female contributors in the fourteen volumes which are covered by this study. This study shows that the average numbers of citations per contributions are maximum in the year 2013 [i.e. 34.40] and the average number of citations per contributions are minimum in the year 2017 in this journal [i.e. 6.8]. It is also clear from the above study that maximum numbers of citations are in the year 2010 [i.e. 408], and minimum numbers of citations are in the year 2023 in this journal [i.e. 69]. It is also an important point to be noted that all the research articles published in this journal are carrying proper citations. It can be said from this research that Journals and Books are mostly cited by the authors of this journal. As we are now living in the electronic age, the virtual libraries and virtual information centres are playing an important role regarding information retrieval and dissemination. The authors are cited the electronic documentary resources very frequently. The other documents like thesis, dissertations, working papers, reports, conference papers etc. are also cited by the authors of this journal. After completion of this study, it may be said that 'Biofuel Production and Utilization' is the main thrust area of this journal. Maximum

research papers are published in this journal are on 'Biofuel Production and Utilization'. It is also clear from this particular study that 'Biotechnology', 'Biochemistry', 'Bioclimatology', 'Biodiversity', 'Biosciences', 'Biodegradation', 'Bioelectricity', 'Biodynamics' are also very important fields of research. The other micro-subjects under 'Biofuels' are also attracted by the researchers in the concerned subject discipline. It is also clear from this study that the research articles are also published in the following thrust areas: - 'Biogas', 'Bio-Geochemistry', 'Bioethics', 'Bio-electrochemistry', 'Biogenesis', and 'Biogeography'. The researchers are published their research papers in the above-mentioned areas also. This journal is an internationally reputed, peer reviewed, prospective, and potential journal and it has been achieved its position among the scientists, technologists, researchers, and the scholars of the related disciplines. The scientists and technologists are hopeful about the diversified nature of articles published in this journal.

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